

1 First report of Bacterial Leaf Streak disease of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*
2 in Tanzania

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12 Bacterial Leaf Streak (BLS), caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* (*Xoc*), has emerged
13 as a significant threat to rice production in Africa, ranking as the second most important
14 bacterial disease of rice on the continent. BLS presence in Africa was first documented by visual
15 observation in the 1980s in West Africa and in Madagascar. The first strains of *Xoc* isolated
16 and confirmed by molecular analysis came from diseased leaves collected between 2003 and
17 2013 in Mali, Burkina Faso or Madagascar (Gonzalez 2007, Poulin 2014). Today the disease is
18 found in at least nine African countries, including East African countries such as Burundi,
19 Kenya and Uganda. Yield losses attributed to BLS range from 20 to 30% (Sileshi and
20 Gebeyehu, 2021). In Tanzania, where BLS has never been reported, rice is the second most
21 important food crop after maize. BLS is a seed-borne disease and its spread is highly facilitated
22 by trade. The extensive network of rice trade between Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania, suggests
23 that the disease may be present in Tanzania as well. During an initial survey in March 2013, we
24 identified a rice field in the Morogoro region with plants showing typical symptoms of BLS,
25 such as translucent lesions with yellow-brown to black streaks and sometimes exudates on leaf
26 surfaces. Another survey was next conducted in March 2016 in three rice plots owned by KPL,
27 a large rice producer in the Morogoro region. A total of seven symptomatic leaves from both
28 surveys were selected for further analysis. 4 to 5cm long leaf pieces were disinfected, rinsed
29 with sterile water and ground. Then 10 µl of the leaf powder resuspended in 1mL of sterile
30 water was plated on a semi-selective PSA medium and incubated at 28°C for 5 days. 9 colonies
31 from 7 different leaves (two leaves per plot collected in 2016 and one leaf from the 2013 survey)
32 resembling those of *X. oryzae* were isolated and subjected to a pathogenicity test and molecular
33 characterization. The multiplex PCR tool developed for the identification of *X. oryzae* pathovars
34 (Lang et al., 2010) revealed the characteristic amplification pattern of *Xoc* (2 amplicons of
35 331bp and 691bp) for all isolates. The pathogenicity test was performed on 4-week-old plants
36 of *O. sativa* cv. Azucena by infiltration with a needleless syringe of a bacterial suspension with
37 an optical density of 0.5. Leaf streak symptoms were observed one week later, and all nine
38 inoculated *Xoc* strains resulted in the appearance of typical BLS symptoms, similar to those
39 observed after infiltration of the control strain BLS256, while the water-inoculated leaves
40 remained asymptomatic. The isolation of PCR-confirmed *Xoc* strains from these artificially
41 inoculated plants allowed the completion of Koch's postulates. After amplification using
42 primers *XgyrBIF* and *XgyrBIR* (Young et al., 2008) and sequencing (see Suppl. File 1), the
43 analysis of the 541 base pair partial sequence of the *gyrB* housekeeping gene for these 9 strains

44 shows 100% of nucleotide sequence identity with the homologous sequence of the *Xoc*
45 reference strain BLS256 (Acc. No. CP003057). All strains are deposited in the collection of the
46 French Institute for Research on Sustainable Development (IRD) in Montpellier (France), under
47 the accession numbers CIX26, CIX1043, CIX1044, CIX1045, CIX1046, CIX1047, CIX1048,
48 CIX1049, and CIX1050. To our knowledge, this study represents the first molecular
49 confirmation of the presence of BLS in Tanzania.

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51 **References**

52 Gonzalez, C., Szurek, B., Manceau, C., Mathieu, T., Séré, Y., Verdier, V., 2007. Molecular
53 and Pathotypic Characterization of New *Xanthomonas oryzae* Strains from West Africa. *Mol.*
54 *Plant-Microbe Interactions* 20, 534–546.

55

56 Lang, J.M., Hamilton, J.P., Diaz, M.G.Q., Van Sluys, M.A., Burgos, M.R.G., Vera Cruz, C.M.,
57 Buell, C.R., Tisserat, N.A., Leach, J.E., 2010. Genomics-based diagnostic marker development
58 for *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* and *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola*. *Plant Dis.* 94, 311–319.

59

60 Poulin, L., Raveloson, H., Sester, M., Raboin, L.-M., Silué, D., Koebnik, R., Szurek, B., 2014.
61 Confirmation of bacterial leaf streak caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* on rice in
62 Madagascar. *Plant Dis.* 98, 1423–1423.

63

64 Sileshi, G.W., Gebeyehu, S., 2021. Emerging infectious diseases threatening food security and
65 economies in Africa. *Glob. Food Secur.* 28, 100479

66

67 Young, J., Park, D.C., Shearman, H., Fargier, E., 2008. A multilocus sequence analysis of the
68 genus *Xanthomonas*. *Syst. Appl. Microbiol.* 31, 366–377.

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